

ACTIVE METHODOLOGIES LEARNING BY DOING

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This deliverable is aimed to produce a literature review about active methodologies and learning by doing to discover what is the best design to apply in the Syllabus and MOOC.

1. OVERVIEW

1.1. Deliverable short description

The elaboration of the syllabus will be carried out based on a previous investigation. The purpose of this desk research is to find the best methodology, the techniques and exercises that have proved to be efficient in online and on-site learning contexts.

The report will serve to guide how we must do the MOOC. The instructional design of the course and its structure will be similar in both modalities in which it will be offer on-site and on-line (MOOC).

The syllabus will result as a course material, which integrates the content directions and the techniques to be used in the implementation of the course.

The syllabus proposes an innovative model both in the use of active methodologies and in the treatment of the contents.

1.2. Main research questions addressed

- What are the active methodologies and Learning by doing?
- How can we apply these in our Learning activities?
- What are the best methodology, the techniques and the exercise to use both in onsite and online learning activities?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW ANALYSIS

2.1. Active methodologies: learning by doing

Motto:

*For the things we have to learn before we can do them, we learn by doing them.
(Aristotle, The Nicomachean Ethics)*

Access to information has been fundamental to the acquisition of knowledge. The different technological advances throughout history have made information more accessible. In spite of this and being in a historical moment where information is ubiquitous and almost infinite, the mere fact of having content does not guarantee effective learning. Theorists have shown that the most objective and real formula is learning by doing (Koedinger, Kim, Zhuxin McLaughlin, & Bier, 2015), directed towards the student learning process based on problem solving (Anzai, & Simon, 1979) from a constructivist and connectist perspective. It must motivate, it must be realistic, it must create the need for the objective, it must allow sufficient opportunities to practice skills and seek knowledge (Schank, Berman, & Macpherson, 1999).

The epistemic assumptions of constructive learning are different from those of traditional instruction, so classical methods of needs and task analysis are inappropriate for designing constructivist learning environments (CLEs) (Jonassen & Rohrer-Murphy, 1999, pág. 61).

It is curious how, after more than 100 years since John Dewey developed his practical teaching programme with the aim of offering the students of his time an appropriate preparation for a full life, structured didactic strategies are still defended today on the mere information of contents.

We always live at the time we live and not at some other time, and only by extracting at each present time the full meaning of each present experience are we prepared for doing the same thing in the future. This is the only preparation, which in the long run, amounts to anything. (Dewey, 1916, pág. 30)

Dewey's ideas and legacy were strengthened by the work of his friend William Heard Kilpatrick with his Project Approach (1918), as well as studies on the experiential learning model of Simon Priest & Michael Gass (2005), Dick Prouty (2007) or the construction of David Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle (1984).

The knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. (p. 38)

Figure 1. Experiential Learning
 Source: Prepared from David Kolb (1984).

Some of the typologies of activities in active learning models are usually:

- Working on specific projects
- Perform tasks for personal development
 - Field studies
- Acquire experience in extreme situations
- Analyze actions taken and correct errors

As for the didactic strategies of an active model, there are different instruments more in tune with its pedagogical principles. These tend to be: a) online rubrics, since students can compare their activities with those of the rest of their peers, b) the ABP (Project Based Learning), due to the great participation it implies in active and motivating work among students, or c) The electronic portfolio, due to the autonomy that this work modality allows (Gámiz-Sánchez, 2017).

Let us now look at some of the strategies, linked to technologies, of active methods:

2.2. Learning in action

When we apply the term learning in action, we are focusing on a series of learning methods where students, either individually or in small groups, carry out activities in order to solve a series of tasks, challenges or problems in an situated way. Reg Revans, was the first author who used the term and developed the methodology, applying the following formula: $L (\text{learning}) = P (\text{program}) + Q (\text{questions})$. Since the early 1980s, the use of this method has been recommended in American high schools.

In 2004, Michael Marquardt introduced an R for Reflection to the Revans formula: $L (\text{learning}) = P (\text{program}) + Q (\text{questions}) + R (\text{Reflection})$

The weight of each of the elements that make up the formula varies according to the type of active methodology used: ABP (Problem-based or Project Based Learning), PLE (Personal Learning Environment), Question Based Model, Critical Reflection Model, Action Research Model or Programmed Learning Model (Katkalo, Moehrle, & Volkov, 2019).

2.3. Adaptive learning

The fundamental principle of adaptive learning is that learners achieve the same outcomes from individual and differentiated activities based on their experiences, knowledge, skills and habits using technologies. For this it is important that both the contents, the formats (the type of activities) as well as the organization or sequence of the activities are adapted (aulaPlaneta). Examples such as LearnSmart and Knewton, have shown that in adaptive learning students learn

by personalizing their training. But they have also warned that this type of learning implemented in e-learning platforms, requires applications with a great technological development that involve multiple variables and itineraries.

There are examples of adaptive learning models based on games such as the ALGAE model (Adaptive Learning GAME dEsign) (Lavieri, 2015).

Table 1. Fundamental elements in adaptive learning

Collecting data	Collects and processes vast amounts of data about the student's knowledge and skills.
Output system	Transforms data and generates results based on all data collected.
Customization in the system	Harness the power of the system to find the best learning strategy for each student.

Source: based on <https://www.knewton.com>

Image 1. Adaptive learning system.

Source: www.aulapleta.com. <http://cort.as/-RU24>

Likewise, the assessment tests in this type of model must be equally adaptive according to the individual learning path of the student. Some of the tools for developing adaptive tests are: Qualtrics, Google Forms, Typeform or Doodle.

2.4. Placed learning

Gathering John Dewey's ideas about how the learning experience is produced by a geographical, artistic and literary, scientific and historical context, situated learning uses the local community and environment as a starting point for curriculum learning, strengthening community ties, appreciation of the natural world and commitment to citizen participation (Sobel, 2004). As a methodology adapted to current technological development allows students, through the creation of "real" projects:

... understand the professional dynamics and the routines and demands that are necessary in this context; in short, the aim is to put them in a simulated situation in which the knowledge acquired has to be applied to the search for solutions aimed at achieving effective products. (Gértrudix and García, page 26)

2.5. Blended learning

Blended learning is the combination of traditional forms of classroom learning with elements of e-learning (video, audio, graphics, networked information, etc.). Currently, 50% of American classrooms use this type of methodology.

The most used models are:

1. Change of format. The educational programme that alternates remote synchronous components (e.g. webinars), asynchronous e-learning, structured self-learning and group work. A clear example is Virtual Classrooms with Learning Management Systems (LMS): a software application designed to integrate learning tools, as well as to administer, manage and distribute learning programs and generate learning analyses and reports. It is important to highlight the magnitude of applications and software products that have been appearing from LMS in the last decade giving all kinds of solutions to businesses and educational institutions.

Product	Deployment	Organizations Served	Learning Type	eCommerce	Gamification	Mobile Learning	Social Learning	Video Conferencing	
Docebo ★★★★★ (94 reviews)	☐ ☁		Blended	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Visit Website
Cornerstone LMS ★★★★★ (102 reviews)	☐ ☁		Blended	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Visit Website
iSpring Learn ★★★★★ (79 reviews)	☐ ☁		Blended	☐	✓	✓	✓	✓	Visit Website
Firmwater LMS ★★★★★ (55 reviews)	☁		Blended	✓	☐	✓	☐	☐	Visit Website
eFront ★★★★★ (30 reviews)	☐ ☁		Blended	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Visit Website
uQuallo ★★★★★ (4 reviews)	☁		Blended	☐	✓	✓	✓	☐	Visit Website
TalentLMS ★★★★★ (281 reviews)	☐ ☁		Blended	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Visit Website
Lanteria HR ★★★★★ (4 reviews)	☐ ☁			☐	☐	✓	✓	☐	Visit Website
Engagedly ★★★★★ (67 reviews)	☐ ☁			☐	✓	☐	✓	☐	Visit Website
SkillCast ★★★★★ (2 reviews)	☁			☐	✓	☐	☐	☐	Visit Website

Image 2. Applications and software products in LMS

Source: <https://www.capterra.com>

2. Flipped Classroom. Mixed learning, with direct transfer of knowledge in which the instructor becomes a kind of guide.
3. Autonomous group. The class is divided into two groups. One of them works in a traditional way and the other using technology.

2.6. Online Learning

Faced with the great demand for higher education in the world, with an increase of more than 5% per year as well as the increase and availability by users of increasingly advanced and accessible technology, institutions have opted to offer many of their studies and content in a non-presential way.

There are some 150.6 million tertiary students globally, roughly a 53% increase over 2000. In low-income countries tertiary-level participation has improved only marginally, from 5% in 2000 to 7% in 2007. Sub-Saharan Africa has the lowest participation rate in the world (5%). In Latin America, enrolment is still less than half that of high-income countries. Attendance entails significant private costs that average 60% of GDP per capita. (Altbach, Reisberg & Rumbley, 2009, pág. VI)

Distance education has always been present, in one form or another. Already in the letters from Plato to Dionysus and in the letters from Pliny the Elder to Pliny the Younger we could find an incipient educational practice at a distance. The first reference to "correspondence" education is found in the material offered by Caleb Philipps in the Boston Gazette on March 20, 1728 which will mark the beginning of a different way in the acquisition of knowledge. Since then, the history of distance education can be divided into four stages or generations: 1) Correspondence

Teaching; 2) Multimedia Teaching; 3) Telematic Teaching and 4) Training through Internet or e-learning (García Aretio, 2001).

Any persons in the country desirous to learn this art, may by having the several Lessons sent weekly to them, be as perfectly instructed as those that live in Boston (Battenberg, 1971, 44)

Image 3. History of MOOCs.
Source Taken from P. Hill 2012

In addition to the larger global platforms (Coursera, edX, FutureLearn), many national governments around the world have launched their own country-specific MOOC platforms, including India, Mexico, Thailand, Italy, and Israel. (Shah & Pickard, 2019)

Imagen 4. MOOC providers around the world
Source: <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-providers-list>.

Table 1. *Comparative table of MOOC, Inverted Classroom and B-learning.*

	MOOC	Inverted classroom	Combined Learning
Year of appearance.	2012	2002	At the end of the 90's.
Place of creation	University of Mantioba Canada.	University of Miami (Ohio).	Not defined.
Place of creation	Modality of formation with proposals oriented to the diffusion web of contents.	A learning model where the contents are previously reviewed, and the activities are carried out in class in a participative and active way.	Modality of studies that mixes classroom classes and technology in a way that leads to a well-balanced educational design.
Responsible in charge of structure and contentstructure and contents	The teacher or experts in the specific area of the course.	The same teacher or a team of teachers.	The same teacher or a team of teachers.
Figure of the teacher	With little participation in the teaching and learning process.	Instructor, guide and promoter of significant learning (In charge of elaborating the audiovisual material of previous consultation to class).	Instructor, guide and promoter of significant learning. As well as mediator and dynamizer.
Student Figure	With a strong commitment to self-learning.	Highly active, with a strong commitment to acquire conceptual knowledge through pre-class videos.	Highly active, since teaching methods focus on him.
Number of students	Massive (from hundreds to thousands of students).	Medium or small groups (30 to 10 students).	Medium or small groups (30 to 10 students).
Audiovisual tools	Used with the reservation of the person in charge of the course.	Used for theoretical and conceptual explanation.	Used at the teacher's discretion.
Digital reference material	Used.	Used.	Used.
Virtual platform	Completely the course is developed on a virtual platform.	The blended learning section is developed in the virtual platform.	The blended learning section is developed in the virtual platform taking advantage of the best of E-learning.
Classroom	Not applicable.	Of quality, where activities, discussions and practices are approached.	Implemented taking advantage of the best of face-to-face classes.
Online Class	Applies in full.	It only applies to the consultation of materials.	Implemented taking advantage of the best of online classes.
Evaluation Form	Not very complex, most with the approach of self-regulation and	Completely in charge of the teacher, where the student	Completely in charge of the teacher, where the

	immediate verification of self-assessments.	is analyzed to ensure significant knowledge after observing weaknesses or deficiencies of the student.	student is analyzed to ensure significant knowledge.
Collaborative work	In some courses apply.	Very applied.	You can apply.

Source: translated from Zepeda, Díaz, Salcedo & Tapia, 2018, pp. 169-170.

2.7. War Gaming

The company Avalon Hill is the pioneer and the most specialized in war games and strategic board games. He has also dedicated himself to role-playing games and sports simulations.

The main antecedents and influences of war gaming are as follows:

- **Kriegspiel (1811).** A war game developed by the Prussian army in the 19th century to teach battlefield tactics to officers.
- **Strategists (1880).** A series of American war games, based on military principles and designed to help both beginners and advanced students in prosecuting the entire study of tactics, great tactics, strategy, military history and various war operations.
- **Little Wars (1913).** is one of the first known regulations for [miniature games](#). It was developed in 1913 by the British writer [H. G. Wells](#).
- **The Fletcher Pratt Naval War Game (1940).** This is a set of naval miniature game rules for the naval battles of World War I and World War II,
- **Tactics (Charles Roberts, self.published, 1953/Avalon Hill, 1958).** It is the first modern war game on board that was commercialized.
- **Gettysburg (Avalon Hill, 1958).** First board war game based on a historical battle: The American Civil War.
- **Diplomacy (Avalon Hill, 1961).** It was the first board war game to be played by mail (postcard) and its main feature lies in the players' bargaining power. It is a precedent of email games generalized from the 80's.
- **Chainmail (Lake Geneva Tactical Studies Association, 1969/Guidon Games, 1971).** First professional strategy game

2.8. Role-Playing Simulation

An equation can be written that explains the origin of role-playing as a marriage between the literary tradition of fantasy and the tradition of board war games (Mackay, 2001): Fantasy+Literature+Wargames=Role-Playing Games.

The term simulation is complex and can be identified with multiple expressions such as "simulation," "game," "role-play," "simulation-game," "role-play simulation," and "role-playing game" (Crookall and Oxford, 1990a).

Role-playing encourages thinking and creativity, allowing students to develop and practice new language and behavioral skills, as well as encourage motivation and participation. (Tompkins, 1998).

Role-playing simulations are frequently claimed to be effective pedagogical tools in the teaching of international relations (IR); however, there is a surprising lack of empirical evidence on their classroom utility. (Raymond, 2010.pág. 51).

The steps in a Role Play Simulation are:

1. Assign roles
2. Investigate the subject.
3. Objective and problem to solve.
4. Group work in the simulation.
5. Carry out the evaluation report.
6. Final discussion.

Finally, students can verbalize their feelings and thoughts on the topic of role-play simulation in order to improve the next simulation.

Simulation is an interactive learning model about processes, events, places or real situations. This is done by creating environments where students develop specific skills and experience the impact of decisions that require a certain level of risk.

Some types of simulations are: a) Branched history, where the student makes decisions from different narrative options; b) Simulation with system dynamics, based on a mathematical model, in which each decision has a complex impact on the performance of the entire system, and c) Simulator, to simulate control over a process, instrument or vehicle.

2.9. Active methodologies to train specialist

As we have already mentioned, active methods are the best suited to the individual learning of each student. When we talk about specialized training, this type of methods becomes more evident. From the 90's until today, the incorporation of methodological strategies more adapted to each student's way of learning have been favoured thanks to the appearance of different technologies. In this sense, we have gone from a passive model (traditional education), with an almost exclusively conceptual approach through instruments such as conferences, seminars or workshops; to active models (mixed education) using tests, role-playing, case method, round table, etc., or interactive models (educational innovation) using strategies such as simulators, interactive training, situated or e-learning technologies, until today we have seen integrated models using 3D simulations and Virtual Reality (Alexander Ershov & Stepanova, 2012).

Current studies have researched the type of methodologies using technologies that are best adapted for the development of competencies among journalists. The main skills that are improved are linked to the ability to acquire new knowledge and skills, the ability to lead the creation of an effective communication infrastructure of the organisation, the ability for scientific research or the ability to interpret and present the results of scientific research (Klyuev, Poznin, & Zubko, 2019).

2.10. Active methodologies in MOOC

To be successful in an MOOC, a self-generated learning environment supported by students who want to support and share ideas with others should be promoted, although there may also be some manipulation of information by some students. In the MOOC forums the students who participate the most are the most involved. In order to do so, they must be familiar with the functioning of the discussion forums that constitute one of the best allies for solid learning.

How to lessen preferential attachment effects to maintain efficient information transmission as well as increase robustness of a discussion forum in the design of a networked learning environment is key to the development of sustainable MOOCs. (Zhang, Skryabin & Song, 2016, pág. 282)

Increasing the level of reciprocity and transitivity in scalable discussions seems to be a useful strategy that deserves serious attention.

Due to the large number of registered students, it is difficult for MOOC instructors to interact with individual students on an individual basis. (Bruff, Fisher, McEwen, & Smith (2013).

The value of MOOCs comes when you use them to create hybrids that are the best of both worlds. Rather than having the instructor lectures during class and then send the students home with assignments, many instructors are now using MOOCs to flip the classroom. (Gates, 2013)

The Automatic Control Lab at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne proposes a MOOC for the first course on control. This MOOC differs from standard MOOCs since it focuses on the hands-on sessions that are associated to the ex-cathedra classes. The usual MOOC video-quiz learning scenario is enhanced with the use of remote laboratories (labs), online simulations, and analysis and controller designs tools forming a Massive Open Online Lab (MOOL) which enables interactive experimentation (Salzmann, Piguet & Gillet, 2019)

Example of simulation of a Massive Open Online Lab (MOOL) implemented in eDx . Steps in a sequence of simulated activities of a remote laboratory (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne. MOOC Control Systems):

Steps	Activity
Presentation Video	<p>Vidéo Identifications de paramètres</p> <p>Video - module 1</p> <p>Model transfer function</p> $G_w(s) = \frac{\omega_w}{1 + s^2}$ <p>What is the dynamic relationship between input [volt] and output speed [volt]?</p>

Steps to find the linear range:

Instructions

- Connect to the system (**Remote experimentation** tab)
- Select the **open-loop & speed** modes
- Increase the motor voltage, starting from 0 [V]
- Observe when the disc starts to turn
 - Take note of the applied voltage
- Keep increasing the voltage until saturation
 - Take note of the applied voltage when reaching the saturation
- Report the linear range in the next tab

Distance Experimentation

Analysis and validation

Numerical Input
2 points possible (ungraded)

What is the linear range for

Enter the minimal value:

Enter the maximal value:

Submit

Peer-to-peer discussion

Questions
Bookmark this page

Est-ce que la zone linéaire est similaire si vous appliquez des tensions négatives au moteur?
Est-ce que l'amplitude du saut de tension appliqué influence les paramètres identifiés ?

Discussion
Topic: Week 1 / Topic-Level Student-Visible Label

Show all posts

Question 1 6/2
1. If I put on the negative voltage, the result is the same unless it spins on the opposite direction. Without that, it acts the same way. 2. It does not change unless we modify th...

Response
Est-ce que la zone linéaire est similaire si vous appliquez des tensions négatives au moteur? A) Yes. It is quite similar with positive linear range and negative linear range. In m...

Responses aux questions
Si on applique une tension négative le gain va changer mais la zone linéaire restera inchangée. Le saut de tension n'aura pas d'influence sur les paramètres que si on se trou...

REPOSE
ces différents paramètres doivent rester inchangés , vu qu'ils sont des paramètres propres (intrinsèques) à notre appareil

REPOSE
ces différents paramètres doivent rester inchangés , vu qu'ils sont des paramètres propres (intrinsèques) à notre appareil

question 1
Lorsque l'on met une tension négative, la zone linéaire ne change pas. Le gain change mais pas la constante de temps.

Modifications/alternatives MOOC

By restriction of the participants		Design and execution methods	
BOOC	Similar to MOOC but has fewer participants (50-60)	DOCC	collaborative online course distributed in different universities with equal content but managed independently.
SOOC	MOOC with admission requirements (initial knowledge test). The more restrictive the access, the	GCOS	Massive synchronous online course, is a type of MOOC expert (xMOOC) with live transmissions.

	greater the collaboration of the participants could be.		
<i>COOC</i>	MOOC restricted to a company's target audience.	<i>POOC</i>	Personalized open online course. with technology for content management and the pace of learning based on the cognitive and behavioral response capacity of students.
<i>TORQUE</i>	Focused on quality and effectiveness. The completion of a course of this type is considered a prerequisite for the study of a particular discipline or tool.	<i>S-POC</i>	online course with a high degree of flexibility in which the learner can individually select the pace of learning and the section of the course in which they wish to start learning.

Table 2. MOOC Providers

Country	Providers	Link
U.S.A.	Coursera	https://www.coursera.org
	edX	https://www.edx.org
	Udacity	https://www.udacity.com
France	FUN	https://www.fun-mooc.fr
Germany	Iiversity	https://iversity.org
Spain	Miriadax	https://miriadax.net/home
United Kingdom	FutureLearn	https://www.futurelearn.com
Middle East	Rwaq	https://www.rwaq.org
	Edraak	https://www.edraak.org
Australia	Open2study	https://www.classcentral.com

Examples of MOOCs for journalists on the Coursera platform

First name	Summary	Registered	liaison
Become a Journalist: Report the News! Launch Your Journalism Career. Develop journalistic skills for print, broadcast and social media platforms.	This specialization will develop and improve your understanding of the global field of journalism. You'll learn best practices and ethical standards for news gathering processes and the compilation of a news report through hands-on projects, peer feedback, and problem exploration. It will also study the impact of journalism on social issues and trends, as well as explore career opportunities in newspapers, magazines, social media, Internet multimedia, television, radio, corporate and community journalism.	5.300	http://cort.as/RUAe
Español para Journalismo	This course is designed for non-native English speakers who are interested in developing the skills necessary for a career in modern journalism.	101.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/journalism
Journalism, the future, and you!	You'll learn about the careers that are available in journalism, and what opportunities a journalist's skill set can offer in other fields. He will explore areas such as being an international correspondent, self-publishing in journalism, as well as how to work as a freelance in the field. You will have the power to develop your own path in journalism, from being an active and informed consumer to being a journalist.	10.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/international-journalism
Transmedia Storytelling: Narrative worlds, emerging technologies, and global audiences	This course will help you design a strategy to develop and tell your own transmedia story.	30.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/transmedia
How to Write and Publish a Scientific Paper (Project-Centered Course)	In this project-based course, a complete scientific paper will be outlined, an appropriate journal will be chosen to which the completed paper will be sent for publication, and a checklist will be prepared that will allow you to judge independently whether your paper is ready to be submitted.	53.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/how-to-write-a-scientific-paper

Visualization for Data Journalism	The purpose of this class is to learn to think about the visual presentation of data, how and why it works, and how to do it the right way. We'll learn how to make graphics like The New York Times, Vox, Pew and FiveThirtyEight. In the end, you can share your beautiful graphics in publications, blogs and websites.	0	https://www.coursera.org/learn/visualization-for-data-journalism
What is news?	This course will guide you through the basics of professional journalism and the values of news and ethics of covering real-world topics and events.	14.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/what-is-news
Gathering and Developing the News	Journalists develop information through interviews and sources. The most successful journalists quickly master these important skills. The course will also teach you how to find information, interview skills, and how to process information from various sources for publication.	7.500	https://www.coursera.org/learn/gathering-the-news
Making Sense of the News: News Literacy Lessons for Digital Citizens	This course will help students develop their critical thinking skills so that they can better identify reliable information in news reports and be better informed about the world in which we live.	11.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/news-literacy
International Humanitarian Law in Theory and Practice	In this course, Prof. Robert Heinsch, Dr. Giulia Pinzauti and Dr. Emma Irving will give you a deep insight into the rules that govern armed conflicts, and their aim is to mitigate human suffering on the battlefield.	12.000	https://www.coursera.org/learn/international-humanitarian-law

Source: <https://www.coursera.org/courses?query=journalism>

The screenshot shows the Coursera interface for a course titled "What is news and who decides?". On the left is a sidebar with navigation options: "Un vistazo", "Semana 1" through "Semana 6", "Calificaciones", "Notas", "Foros de debate", "Mensajes" (with a notification icon), "Recursos", and "Información del Curso". The main content area displays the course title and a row of seven profile pictures. Below this, a section titled "What makes journalism different from other types of information?" lists several activities: a video (2 min), a reading (10 min), another video (4 min), another reading (10 min), a video (5 min), another reading (10 min), and a discussion board (5 min). At the bottom, an "Assignment" section shows a "Cuestionario" (Quiz) with 9 questions and a deadline of "Vencimiento 6 de oct. de 23:59 PDT".

All courses have the same structure:

1. Explanatory videos (two or three per topic) with different formats (moution, presentations, explaining teachers, etc.).
2. Recommended readings
3. Evaluation exercises (test)
4. Discussion forums by topic.

One of the limitations of many online courses is that they lack sufficiently rich and well-supported activities for adaptive learning. In this sense, it would be expected that this type of courses could offer activities with a greater degree of interactivity, thus strengthening the learning of the students enrolled. (Koedinger, Kim, Zhuxin, McLaughlin & Bier, 2015).

3. ANALYSIS

For the final MOOC proposal, the characteristics of the different types of MOOC according to Pernías and Luján (n/d) have been taken into account:

- Network-based: they do not focus on the transmission of content or the acquisition of skills, but on the relationships established between course participants. The evaluation that is traditionally used cannot be used in these courses.
- Task-based: the most important thing is the acquisition of certain aptitudes and skills through the realization of activities. Creating a community of learners is important for example exchange and mutual help, but it is not the main thing.

- Content-based: the most important thing is the acquisition of the content. The creation of a community of students is secondary and a student can pass the course without relating to the rest of the students. The traditional evaluation by means of exercises of type test is the one that is used in this type of courses. xMOOC

Thus, according to these aspects mentioned above, the cMOOC or courses with a connectivist pedagogical approach would be referenced in the first place; the hybrid courses or hMOOC/tMOOC defined in the second place and finally the xMOOC or courses based mainly on the contents. In order to be able to discern the MOOC typology that best fits the final proposal, a conceptual map of the different MOOCs with their main characteristics is shown below.

REFERENCES:

- Cabero, J., Lorente, M.C. y Vázquez Martínez, A.
- Fidalgo, A. M. Luisa Sein-Echaluze, M.L. y García-Peñalvo, F.J.
- Pernías, P. y Luján, S.
- Ruiz Bolívar, C.
- Lugton, M.
- Scopeo Informe nº2: MOOC
- Martí, J.

3.1. MOOCs that use actives methodologies

Example of analysis: MOOC "Poténciate con redes sociales" (Poténciate con redes sociales)

The MOOC "Poténciate con redes sociales", by Professor Oriol Borrás Gené, has as its main objective to raise awareness of the possibilities offered by the Internet to convert the fingerprint into a personal brand by making use of the RSS. This MOOC was awarded the first prize in the MiriadaX Innovation Awards 2018.

Firstly, it meets the requirements indicated by Castaño and Cabero (2013) and they must meet this type of courses such as:

- It is an educational resource that has a certain resemblance to a class, to a classroom.
- With start and end dates.
- It has evaluation mechanisms.
- It's online.
- Free to use.
- It is open through the web and has no admission criteria.
- Enables large-scale interactive participation by hundreds of students. (2013,89)

Likewise, it is an hMOOC (hybrid), as Borrás, Martínez and Martín (2019) point out, students are given greater prominence (cMOOC) and a platform is used to share contents (xMOOC) together with external tools that promote the social side and allow new methodologies to be used such as gamification (badges, reputation, points, etc.).

In terms of structure, this course has the following characteristics:

It includes a video about that allows to give diffusion of the course.

The MOOC course has four theoretical modules, independently of module 0 or learning guide, which must be carried out during one month in a participative and collaborative way and whose estimated duration is 20 hours of work. The material will be available from the first day, with the exception of the evaluable activities which are carried out every week. In addition, additional content and volunteers are included.

The list of modules is as follows:

- Module 0. Learning guide. Introduction and operation.
- Module 1. State of the art of personal digital identity
- Module 2. Professional digital identity management.
- Module 3. LinkedIn and other professional networks
- Module 4. Towards a personal brand

Thus, it is in the module 0 or introductory where the keys are given necessary for the operation of the course, dates, evaluations, certificates.

The first two modules work on digital identity and analyse the fingerprint left on the Internet.

The third module deals with professional social networks focused on labour relations such as LinkedIn.

The last module aims to create the personal brand of each participant.

Each module is divided into a series of lessons on a specific subject and can be video or text lessons that include resources such as: links, summaries, infographics, definitions, examples and additional information.

Also, each module has volunteer activities distributed among all the lessons that can be shared. In the same way, weekly events are held that can be followed through different devices and where the possibility of participating is offered, such as the use of the kahoot application in contest format or voting the best question and launching it during the interview with the interviewee.

As regards asynchronous communication, this is done via e-mail with warnings of the most relevant milestones and questions are raised in a facebook group.

The ultimate aim of the course was to create a learning community on Facebook or communication space for collaborative sharing and discussion.

In order to pass the course, four evaluation tests must be carried out, one for each module and with a minimum grade of 5. In these tests, several attempts are allowed and feedback is given.

Finally, in terms of gamification, elements inherent to SSR such as Facebook or Twitter have been taken into account, such as "receiving likes in publications" or getting digital badges or badges when evaluating the activities of other colleagues.

3.2. Real possibilities and limits of edX platform to include actives methodologies

EdX MOOC DEVELOPMENT CHECKLIST – MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS	
Course Announcement and Introduction	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Pre-requisites and learner background for the course are stated	<input type="checkbox"/>
Expected time commitment for learners is stated	<input type="checkbox"/>
Instructor introduction or bio available on about page	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intro to course requests learners view edX Demo101; or intro to platform included in courseware tab	<input type="checkbox"/>
A prompt is provided to the learner on the course info page on how to get started with the course.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course Structure	
Syllabus or course calendar provided (course topics and important dates, including exams)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Grading criteria and certificate requirements posted in the course.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Learning objectives, goals, and outcome(s) posted in the course.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Instructional Materials and Assessments	
Course includes interleaved videos and exercises	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course includes gradable assignments, e.g., exercises/homework/quizzes and assigns a grade	<input type="checkbox"/>
Assessment deadlines are clearly articulated	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course adheres to edX accessibility guidelines	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course provides transcriptions for all videos	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course Administration and Learner Engagement	
Welcome Email sent to learners	<input type="checkbox"/>
Paced emails sent throughout course run	<input type="checkbox"/>
Closing email sent at the conclusion of the course	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course team provides forum moderation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Guidelines provided for the use of forums, forum etiquette	<input type="checkbox"/>
Explanation posted of how to get help with learner issues	<input type="checkbox"/>

Course releases content in consistent manner as laid out in syllabus, changes announced ahead of time	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welcome message on course info page at the beginning of the course	<input type="checkbox"/>

EdX MOOC DEVELOPMENT CHECKLIST – BEST PRACTICES (optional):	
Course Announcement and Introduction	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Welcome/Introduction Video	<input type="checkbox"/>
Optional Self-assessment provided that identifies pre-requisites needed to earn a certificate.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course Structure	
Academic Policy/Collaboration guidelines posted in course.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Instructional Materials and Assessments	
Consistent video quality and audio levels	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course uses pre and post production techniques that enhance instructional content	<input type="checkbox"/>
Required materials and optional materials are delineated inside the course	<input type="checkbox"/>
Video segments average between 3 to 10 minutes	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course provides an online textbook, online notes, or readings	<input type="checkbox"/>
Downloadable copies of presentations materials used in videos provided inside courseware	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cross linking between videos, exercises, textbook are provided within the course	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course includes interactives such as virtual labs or user controlled animations.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course Administration and Learner Engagement	
Course uses a wiki for learner collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/>
Learners are encouraged to use the discussion forum to introduce themselves	<input type="checkbox"/>
Course states availability of course materials for learners once the course has concluded archived	<input type="checkbox"/>
Learners are surveyed at the beginning, during, and close of course	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wiki pre-populated with questions and learner activities	<input type="checkbox"/>

After the analysis of the edX platform based on instructional design ("MDC") the aspects that could be undertaken without difficulties would be those relating to minimum requirements such as: dissemination and introduction, course structure, educational resources and evaluation activities. On the other hand, it would be necessary the tutoring of the course either by the teaching team or other dynamizers to be able to approach the management of the course as far as the participation of the students in the forums of debates or as a tool of communication for doubts/consultations or delivery of activities that promote the interaction between the participants.

In this sense, the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (UAM) describes an edX MOOC as follows:

On the edX platform, courses are organized in sections (usually each section corresponds to one week of student work). These are divided into sub-sections, each of which presents a learning sequence, and the latter are integrated by a series of components (videos, web pages, exercises and discussion forum). This structure of the courses facilitates their dynamism, since the student will have at his disposal every week of work: didactic materials, intercalated exercises between the materials, activities of evaluation and activities to favor the social interaction between them.

edX also allows the introduction of interactive elements (simulators, animations, interpreters, etc.), as well as a wide variety of exercises (Multiple Choice, Drag & Drop, free text response, among others).

In the same way, and following the line of the UAM that includes virtual or simulation laboratories in the additional recommendations, it should be specified that the review of literature regarding MOOC that incorporates these educational resources are oriented towards subjects related to engineering or in Degrees such as Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Mathematics, Science,... Example: University of Colorado Boulder (Link)

Under pressure

Balancing chemical Equations

Changes and forms of energies

4. BIBLIOGRAPHY

Altbach, Ph. G.; Reisberg, L. & Rumbley, L. E. (2009). *Trends in Global Higher Education: Tracking an Academic Revolution*. Paris: UNESCO. Retrieved from <http://cort.as/-RX7m>

Alexander Ershov, A. & Stepanova, E. (2012). The analysis of innovative educational technologies' development in training of Customs business specialists in the eurasian economic community countries. *Customs Scientific Journal*, 1. Retrieved from http://212.1.86.13/jspui/bitstream/123456789/2054/1/CSJ_special-edition-SDF24-31.pdf

Anzai, Y & Simon, H. A. (1979). The theory of learning by doing. *Psychological Review*, 86(2), 124-140

Battenberg, R. W. (1971). The Boston Gazette. March 20, 1728. *Epistolodidaktika*, 1, 44-45.

Belloch, C. (July 31, 2013). *Instructional Design*. University of Valencia. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2kJqUMw>

Borrás-Gené, O.; Martínez-Núñez, M. & Martín-Fernández, L. (2019). Enhancing Fun through Gamification to Improve Engagement in MOOC. *Informatics 2019*, 6, 28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics6030028>

- Bruff, D. O., Fisher D. H., McEwen K. E., & Smith B. E. (2013). Wrapping a MOOC: Student perceptions of an experiment in blended learning. *MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 9(2), 187-199. Retrieved from http://jolt.merlot.org/vol9no2/bruff_0613.pdf
- Cabero, J., Llorente, M.C. & Vázquez Martínez, A. (2014) Las tipologías de MOOC: su diseño e implicaciones educativas. *Faculty, Journal of Curriculum and Faculty Development*, 18(1), 13-25.
- Crookall, D., & Oxford, R. L. (1990). Linking language learning and simulation/gaming. In D. Crookall & R. L. Oxford (Eds.), *Simulation, gaming, and language learning* (pp. 3-24). New York: Newbury House.
- Dewey, Jh. (1916;1944) *Democracy and Education: an introduction to the philosophy of education*. New York: The Macmillan Company.
- Fidalgo, Á., Sein-Echaluce, M.L. & García-Peñalvo, F.J. (2013). Cooperative MOOC. An integration between cMOOC and xMOO. In *II International Congress on Learning, Innovation and Competitiveness (CINAIC 2013)*, 481-486.
- Fidalgo-Blanco, Á., Sein-Echaluce, M. L., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2019). D-OCW. A new model to develop dynamic, social OCW courses adapted to real needs. GRIAL Group. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2mjeKih>.
- Fidalgo-Blanco, Á., Sein-Echaluce, M. L., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). From massive access to cooperation: lessons learned and proven results of a hybrid xMOOC/cMOOC pedagogical approach to MOOCs. *International Review of Educational Technology in Higher Education* (13).
- Gámiz-Sánchez, V. M. (2017). ICT-Based Active Methodologies. 7th International Conference on Intercultural Education "Education, Health and ICT for a Transcultural World", EDUHEM 2016, 15-17 June 2016, Almeria, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2017.02.018>
- García Aretio, L. (2001). History of Distance Education. Madrid: UNED. Retrieved from <https://www.biblioteca.org.ar/libros/142131.pdf>
- Gates, B. (2013). *Association of Community College Trustees' leadership meeting in Seattle*, October 2013 (gatesfoundation.org)
- Gértrudix Barrio, F. & García García, F. (2011). Placed and cooperative learning in higher education: An experience with teams working in communication sciences. *Linhas*, 12(2), 18-30.
- Hill, P. (2012). Online Educational Delivery Models: A Descriptive View. *EDUCAUSE Review*, 47(6), 84-86. Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/113883/>.
- Jonassen, D. H. & Rohrer-Murphy, L. (1999). Activity theory as a framework for designing constructivist learning environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 47(1), 61-79
- Katkalo, V.; Moehrle, M. and Volkov, D. (2019). *Reference dictionary Corporate Learning For the digital World*. Moscow: Sberbank Corporate University. https://efmdglobal.org/wp-content/uploads/Corporate_Dictionary_EN_13.12.18_final.pdf
- Klyuev, Y., Poznin, V., & Zubko, D. (2019). Teaching Future Journalists Media Research Methodology Using Digital Technologies. *Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie)*, 278-285. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2019.2.278>
- Kilpatrick, W. H. (1918). The Project Method: The Use of the Purposeful Act in the Educative Process. *Teachers College Record*, 19, 319-335. Retrieved from <https://archive.org/details/projectmethodus00kilpgoog/page/n2>
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Koedinger, K. R.; Kim, K.; Zhuxin Jia, J.; McLaughlin, E. A. & Bier, N. L. (2015). Learning is Not a Spectator Sport: Doing is Better than Watching for Learning from a MOOC. *L@S '15 Proceedings of the Second (2015) ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale*, 111-120.
- Lavieri, E. (2015). *Adaptive Learning for Educational Game Design*. Createspace Independent Pub.

- Lugton, M. (23 de Agosto de 2012). *What is a MOOC? What are the different types of MOOC? xMOOCs and cMOOCs*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2mn3tNV>
- Mackay, D. (2001). *The Fantasy Role-Playing Game*. North Carolina (EEUU): McFarland @ Company, Inc., Publishers
- Martí, J. (August 24, 2012). *Types of MOOCs*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/2m1R3Lk>
- Pernías, P. and Luján-Mora, S. (2014). MOOCs: origins, history and types. *Communication and Pedagogy. Special MOOC*. No. 269-270, p. 41-47. =<https://bit.ly/1KxqBgD=-sync:ÛÇÈÀÈÀ>
- Priest, S., & Gass, M. (2005). *Effective leadership in adventure programming*. Champaign, Ill: Human Kinetics.
- Prouty, D., Collinson, R., Panicucci, J., & Project Adventure, I. (2007). *Adventure education: theory and applications*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Raymond, C. (2010). Do Role-Playing Simulations Generate Measurable and Meaningful Outcomes? A Simulation's Effect on Exam Scores and Teaching Evaluations. *International Studies Perspectives*, 11(1), 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1528-3585.2009.00392.x>
- Revans, R. W. (1982) The Origins and Growth of Action Learning. *Creative Education*, 6(23), pp. 23–9. DOI: [10.4236/ce.2015.623252](https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2015.623252)
- Ruíz Bolívar, C. (2015). *The MOOC: an alternative model for university education?* Retrieved from: <https://bit.ly/2msZIGT>
- Salzmann, C.; Piguet, Y. & Gillet, D. (2019). New Tools for MOOC/MOOL to Sustain Continuity of Experimentation in Control. IFAC PapersOnLine, 52-9, 254-259. Retrieved from <http://cort.as/-RWsb>
- Schank, R.; Berman, T. R. & Macpherson, K. A. (1999). Learning by Doing. In: Charles M. Reigeluth (ed.). *Instructional-Design Theories and models. A new paradigm of Instructional Theory*, 161-181.
- Shah, D. & Pickard, L. (Jul 30th, 2019). Massive List of MOOC Providers Around the World. Retrieved from <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-providers-list/>
- Siemens, G. (3 junio 2012). What is the theory that underpins “our” MOOCs? <http://www.elearnspace.org/blog/2012/06/03/what-is-the-theorythat-underpins-our-moocs/>
- Scopeo Report nº2 (June 2013). MOOC: State of the current situation, possibilities, challenges and future". June 2013. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/LrrkDG>
- Sobel, D. (2004). *Place-based Education: Connecting Classrooms & Communities*. USA: The Orion Society.
- Tompkins, P. K. (1998). Role playing/simulation. *The Internet TESL Journal*, IV(8). Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Tompkins-RolePlaying.html>
- Zhang, J.; Skryabin, M. & Song, X. (2016) Understanding the dynamics of MOOC discussion forums with simulation investigation for empirical network analysis (SIENA), *Distance Education*, 37(3), 270-286, DOI: 10.1080/01587919.2016.1226230
- Zepeda Martínez, G.; Diaz Llamas, J. L.; Salcedo Rosales, M. & Tapia Ponce, S. Y. (2018). A theoretical approach to MOOC, Inverted Classroom, and B-Learning: Similarities and differences. *Educatconciencia Magazine*, 20(21),156-173